

Review Article

A Review On Multipurpose Therapeutic Use Of Herbal Gel

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ABSTRACT

In this review the study of traditional plants which are using to prepare herbal gels for multipurpose. Herbal medicines is still the mainstay of about 75-80% of the world's population, mainly in developing countries, for primary health care because of better cultural acceptability, better compatibility with human body and lesser side effects. Herbal medicines consist of plant or its part to treat injuries, disease or illnesses and are used to prevent and treat diseases and ailments or to promote health and healing. Herbal medicines are the oldest form of healthcare known to mankind. From that the Herbal Gel are used topically for treating many disorders. By the extraction of plant herb formulate the herbal gel with adding some components such as Carbopol 934, HPMC K 100 Mand Xanthan gum showed good homogeneity, no skin irritation, good stability and anti-inflammatory activity. The extract shows best and promising activity. Now a day's topical agents are widely used to treat skin conditions.

INTRODUCTION

India has rich tradition of plant based on knowledge of healthcare. The use of the plant-based medication is gradually becoming popular throughout the world.[1] Topical gel preparations are intended for skin application or to certain mucosal surfaces for local action or percutaneous penetration of medicament. Gels are typically semi-solid formulations having a liquid phase that has been thickened with other components. Herbal

remedies are getting increasing patient compliance as they avoid of typical side effects of allopathic medicines.[1] Traditional medicines play an important role in health services around the globe. About three quarters of the world population relies on plants and plant extracts for health care. A large number of Indian medicinal plants are attributed with various pharmacological activities as they contain diversified classes of photochemical. The opioids or non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs,

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widely used to reduce the inflammation of various types, suffer from severe side effects like redness, itching etc. As a result, a search for other alternatives seems to be necessary which would be more beneficial. Gel formulations are used to deliver the drug topically because of easy application, increase contact time and minimum side effects as compare to other topical preparation and oral administration. [2] Medicinal plants are rich in several potential drugs and it holds healthier and harmless alternate to synthetic drugs. Different parts such as leaf, root, stem, fruit, seed, and bark are used to obtain several phytochemical constituents. In addition, medicinal plants are rich in biologically active compounds and play an important role in drug discovery. Extracts of medicinal plants are useful in the treatment of several health problems such as bacterial infections, ulcers, arthritis [3] and inflammatory [4]. For the obtaining of these drugs used various types of extraction methods such as maceration method, Soxhlet apparatus methods, percolation method, distillation etc. Herbal gel is a solid, jelly-like substance that can have properties ranging from soft and weak to hard and tough preparation. It is used topically for a variety of purposes, such as protectants, antiseptics, and antimicrobials. The herbal gel was made by using various traditional plants which are applicable for treatment of different disorders like anti-inflammatory activity, anti-ulcer activity, anti-diabetic activities, allergies, arthritis, anticonvulsants, wound healing etc. The plants including *Cynodon Dactylon* linn, *Punica Ganatum*, *thymus vulgaris*, *vitex neugondo* etc. The plant *cynodon dactylon* is a medicinal plant having family poaceae is used in clinical practice and having anti-inflammatory activity, wound healing, anti-diabetic and many others. By the using Soxhlet extraction formulate herbal gel. Other drugs are mentioned in below.

ADVANTAGES OF GEL FORMULATIONS: [5,6]

The gel formulation has several key benefits over conventional semisolid dose formulations

1. Compared to other formulations, gels are simple to manufacture.
2. Gel is a sophisticated, non-greasy composition.
3. Gels offer fantastic adhesion to the application region.
4. Gels are eco-friendly and biocompatible.
5. Be incredibly resilient to stressful situations.

DISADVANTAGES OF GEL FORMULATION: [7,8]

Despite having a number of benefits. Gel formulations can come with certain drawbacks.

1. Gels have a more gradual and persistent effect.
2. The additives or gelators could irritate people.
3. The risk of microbial or fungal assault on gel is increased by the presence of water.
4. The formulation's solvent loss dries to gel.
5. In some gels, flocculation results in an unstable gel.

Ideal properties of topical gel: [9]

1. The gel should be uniform and transparent.
2. When shear or force is applied during the container's shaking, the gel should break easily.
3. The gel should have an inert composition.
4. The gel must not be sticky.
5. The gel shouldn't ever contact with another component in the formulation.
6. The gel must be reliable.
7. The skin or any area where the gel is placed shouldn't be irritated.
8. The gel should be inert in nature.
9. The gel should be non-sticky.
10. The gel should not interact with any other formulation component.
11. The gel should be stable.

12. It should be non-irritate to the skin or any part where the gel is applied.

13. The viscosity is should be optimum.

14. It should have anti- microbial activity.

CLASSIFICATION OF GELS [10]

Gels can be classified based on colloidal phases, nature of solvent used, physical nature and rheological properties

Based on colloidal phases

They are classified into:

a Inorganic (Two phase system)

b Organic (Single phase system)

Inorganic (Two-Phase System)

The system consist of floccules of tiny particles rather than larger molecules and the gel structure will be unstable if the dispersed phase partition size is especially large and develops a three-dimensional structure throughout the gel. They must be thixotropic, which means that when disturbed, they transform from a semisolid to a liquid. Gel made of aluminium hydroxide and bentonite magma is two examples.

Organic (Single Phase System)

On the twisted threads, there are large organic molecules that are continuously dissolved. The majority of organic gels are single-phase solutions made up of organic liquids such Plastic base and gelling agents like carbomer and tragacanthin.

Based on Nature of the Solvent

Hydrogels: (water based):

A hydrogel is three-dimensional networks of hydrophilic polymers that can grows in water and contain a significant quantity of water while maintaining their structural integrity due to the chemical or physical cross-linking of individual polymer chains. Hydrophilic colloids like silica, bentonite, tragacanth, pectin, sodium alginate, etc. provide an example. The hydrogel may be utilised as an ECG medical electrode, rectal medication delivery system, and sustained release drug delivery system.

Organogel: (With a non-aqueous solvent):

A liquid organic phase is contained within a three-dimensional, cross-linked network in an organogel, a type of gel. The addition of a polar solvent causes the organo gelling or gelation of lecithin solution in organic solvents.

Xerogels:

Xerogels are solid-formed gels created by allowing materials to gently dry at room temperature while experiencing unrestricted shrinking. Viscous sintering takes place when a xerogel is heated over a certain point, thereby turning the porous gel into a thick glass. Examples include polystyrene, dry cellulose, and tragacanth ribbons. Gels are occasionally categorized as plastic gels, pseudo-plastic gels, and thixotropic gels because they display non-Newtonian flow.

Based on Physical Nature

Elastic gels:

Agar, pectin, Guar gum, and alginates gels have an elastic property. At the point of junction, the fibrous molecules are joined by comparably weak connections such as hydrogen bonds and dipole attraction. If the molecule has a free -COOH group, a salt bridge of the type -COO-X-COO forms an extra bond between two adjacent strand networks.

e.g.: Alginate and Carbopol

Rigid gels:

This can be made from macromolecules with primary valence bonds connecting the framework. e.g. Silic acid molecules are kept together in a silica gel by the Si-O-Si-O link, resulting in a polymer structure with a network of pores.

There are various types of herbal gel are formulated by using different plant herbs are as follows:

Sr No	Plant Name	Used Part of Plant	Extraction Method	Chemical Constituents	Medicinal Use	Image of Plant
1.	Cynodon Dactylon [11]	Whole Plant	Soxhlet Apparatus Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Terpenoids, • Vitamin • C,Flavonoids • Luteolin, • Orientin, • Neoxanthin, • Saponins, • Volatile Oils. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anti-Inflammatory • Wound Healing, • Anti-Diabetic 	
2.	Caradiosporium halicacabum [11,12]	Leaves	Soxhlet Extractor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1,2,4-trioxolane-2-octanic acid, • 5-octyl methyl ester, ethanol 2 [9-octadecenyloxy] • 1,2,4-Trioxolane-2-octanic acid, • 5octyl methyl ester 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Antibacterial • Antifungal • Antiparasitic • Antidiarrhoeal. 	
3.	Anticardium occidentale linn [13,14]	Leaf	Soxhlet Extractor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ascorbic Acid, • Thiamine • Riboflavin • Niacin 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Antibacterial, • Antifungal, • Antiprotozoal, • Antihelminthic • Antiviral activities 	
4.	Lantana Camara [15,16/17]	Leaves	Microwave	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • L. Camara Are • Germacrene D • Ecaryophyllene • Bicyclogermacren • A-Humulene 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ulcers, • Wounds, • Tumours, • Eczema 	
5.	Piper betle and Thymus vulgaris[18]	Leaves	Soxhlet Extractor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thymol (23%–60%), • Γ-Terpinene (18%–50%), • P-Cymene (8%–44%), • Carvacrol (2%–8%) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anti-Bacterial, • Immunomodulatory, • Antioxidant • Anti-Inflammatory 	

6.	Andrographis Paniculata ^[19,20]	Leaves	Maceration Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diterpenoids, • Flavonoids • Polyphenols 	Anti-bacterial property	
7.	Trigonella foenum Greacum ^[21,22,23]	Seed	Soxhlet Extractor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbohydrates • Proteins, • Lipids, • Alkaloids, • Flavonoids, • Fibers, • Saponins, • Steroidal • Saponins, • Vitamins, • Minerals, Nitrogen 	Anti-inflammatory properties	
8.	Vitex negundo ^[24,25]	Leaves	Hot Extraction Method using Soxhlet Apparatus & Methanol By Cold Maceration Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Terpenoids, • Lignans, • Flavonoids, • Alkaloids • Glycosides 	Anti-Inflammatory Analgesics Activities	
9	Tridax Procumbens ^[26,27]	Leaves	Soxhlet Apparatus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Terpenoids, • Lignans, • Flavonoids, • Alkaloids • Glycosides 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anti-Inflammatory • Analgesics Activities 	
10	Fagonia schweinfurthii ^[28,29]	Plant	Soxhlet Apparatus	alkaloids, starch, protein, tannin, flavonoid, terpenoid, carbohydrates, lignin and phenols	Inflammation, open wounds, boils, skin eruptions, allergies	
11	Turmeric ^[30,31]	Rhizome	Steam Distillation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Curcumin, • Demethoxycurcumin, • Bisdemethoxycurcumin 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skin Cancer, • Small Pox, • Chicken Pox, • Wound Healing, • Urinary tract Infections 	

Acalypha indica ^[32]	Leaves, Stem, Flowers, Used Roots and, Seed	Soxhlet Apparatus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Steroids And Triterpenoid, • Ethanolic Showed The Presence Steroids • Triterpenoids • Glycosides, • Carbohydrate • Alkaloids, • Flavonoids, • Tannins 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anthelmintic • Anti-Inflammation, • Anti-Bacterial, • Anti-Cancer, • Anti-Obesity, • Hepatoprotective • Hypoxia, • Wound Healing Medicine 	
Bael leaf ^[33,34]	Leaves	Soxhlet Apparatus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • βcaryophilene, • viridifloral terpeniol 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anti-inflammatory • Arthritic Disorders 	
Azadirachta Indica ^[35,36]	Leaves	Soxhlet Apparatus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • isomeldenin, • Nimbin, • Nimbinene, 6- • Desacetylnim • Binene, • Nimbandiol, • Immobile, • Nimocinol, • Quercetin, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Antibacterial, • Anthelmintic, • Antiviral, • Anticancer 	
Aloe ^[30]	Leaves	Soxhlet Apparatus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nataloins, • Picric Acid, • Oxalic Acids, • Nitric Acid 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gastrointestinal Disorder, • Atherosclerosis • Coronary Heart Diseases 	
Carica papaya ^[37]	Leaf	Cold Maceration Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ascorbic Acid, • Carpine, • Calcium, • Sodium, • Chymopapain, • Papain. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anti-Inflammatory • Antifungal, • Wound Healing. 	
Solanum lycopersicum ^[38]	Fruit	Supercritical Fluid Extraction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lycopena, • Vitamin, • Protein, • Essential Amino Acids. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skin Inflammation • Dark Spots, • Acneand • Blackheads 	

Fragaria X ananassa [39]	Fruit	maceration process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ascorbic Acid, • Phenolic Compounds • Anthocyanins, • Protosianidin • Flavonoids 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Antiallergic, • Anti Mutagenic, • Antimicrobial, • Anti tumergenic, • Wound Healing. 	
Daucus carota [40]	Fruit	Soxhlet apparatus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moisture • Protein • Fat (0.2%) • Carbohydrate (10.6%), • Rude Fiber • Total Ash • Ca • Fe • P (53 Mg/100 G) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relaxes and Soothes Blood Vessels 	
Citrus sinensis [41]	Fruit	Soxhlet apparatus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limonene, • Ethyl Butanoate, • Octanal, • Decanal, • Hexanal, (S)- • Linalool, • Hydrocarbons, • Alcohols, • Aldehydes, • Esters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acidity, • Stomach Ulcer, • Heartburn 	
Ananas comosus [42]	Fruit	Soxhlet apparatus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gallic Acid, • Syringic Acid, • Vanillin, • Ferulic Acid, • Sinapic Acid, • Coumaric Acid, • Chlorogenic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bacterial infection • Viral infections • Antioxidants • Absorbs ions • Vitamin C deficiency 	

CONCLUSION

The use of Herbal gel getting more popular nowadays because they are more stable and also provide control release than other semisolid dosages forms. The topical gel improves the skin's capacity to absorb medication, increasing bioavailability. A topical administration system's main advantage is that it avoids first-pass metabolism. Additionally, it offers high patient acceptance. The majority of the time, when another method of medication administration has a

lower bioavailability, topical distribution is preferred. Topical gel is a safe and effective therapy option for use in the management of skin-related illnesses, according to the clinical data.[36]

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